

EFFECT OF VIRTUAL MENTORING NETWORKS ON STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of virtual mentoring networks on students' engagement in software engineering in public universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at the 0.05 level of significance guided the study. It adopted quasi-experimental research design using a pre-test and post-test format with non-equivalent groups. The population comprised 84 first year Computer Science Education students. The experimental group consisted of 48 students (40 males and 8 females), while the control group had 36 students. The instrument for this study was "Software Engineering Engagement Test (SEET)". The validity of SEET was established through face and content validation, while its reliability was tested on a group of 20 students using Kuder Richardson Formula 21 which yielded 0.82. The research process involved administering the SEET as a pre-test to both the experimental and control groups before implementing the virtual mentoring networks treatment. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses. The study found that students who learned software engineering through virtual mentoring networks had better engagement than those taught with traditional methods. Their post-test mean scores were noticeably higher. It was also observed that, within the experimental group, male students scored higher than the female students. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended in this study among others that public universities in Bayelsa State should integrate virtual mentoring networks into their teaching methods to improve students' engagement.

Keywords: Virtual Mentoring Networks, Students' Engagement, Software Engineering Federal University Otuoke

Introduction

Education has long been recognized as a vital instrument for both personal growth and societal development. It serves as a mechanism for instilling the right values, beliefs, and character in individuals, enabling them to contribute meaningfully to their communities (Ewim et al., 2020). According to Oyekan (2018), education is a powerful driver of sustainable development, political stability, and economic growth in any nation seeking progress. This transformative role is especially evident in university education, which provides specialized knowledge and skills that prepare individuals to engage effectively in national development.

Universities, as higher education institutions, offer undergraduate and postgraduate programs designed to produce skilled graduates who can meet societal and national demands (Uche, 2016). Beyond academic instruction, universities promote intellectual growth, professional training, and research while fostering innovation, critical thinking, and cultural enrichment (Altbach, 2017). Public universities, in particular, function as crucial centers for knowledge creation and dissemination, offering accessible education that underpins national development and societal advancement. They equip students with the knowledge, skills, and research

opportunities necessary to pursue careers in specialized fields such as software engineering.

Software engineering, as a discipline, involves the systematic development, testing, and deployment of computer applications to solve real-world problems using established engineering principles and best practices (Yasar, 2023). It emphasizes organized approaches to software development that enhance quality, efficiency, and adherence to time and budget constraints. The field encompasses all stages of the software development lifecycle: planning, analysis, design, development, testing, integration, and maintenance (Sommerville, 2016). Software engineers combine technical expertise with problem-solving skills to produce reliable, scalable, and efficient software systems that address business, scientific, and societal needs. By adhering to structured methods, quality assurance, and certification standards, software engineering ensures that software solutions are both dependable and effective.

Software engineering is crucial because it employs systematic methods to design, develop, and manage reliable software that addresses real-world problems effectively. Despite its importance, Ukeh and Nwankwo (2023) reported that the academic performance of Computer Science Education (CSE) students has been unsatisfactory. This poor performance highlights the challenges facing Nigeria's tertiary education system, which appears to be in a state of decay. Lecturers often depend heavily on formal lectures, providing minimal hands-on or project-based learning. As a result, students

struggle to apply theoretical knowledge to practical software engineering tasks (Chinedu-Eze & Bello, 2018).

The adoption of modern pedagogical tools such as active learning, case studies, simulations, and ICT platforms remains limited. Many institutions continue to rely on traditional teaching methods despite calls for more innovative approaches. Infrastructural and resource constraints including inadequate laboratory equipment, limited software tools, and poor internet access further hinder students' engagement with practical software engineering concepts, creating gaps in competence. The effectiveness of software engineering education, therefore, largely depends on the teaching methods employed, emphasizing the critical role of instructional approaches.

Teaching methods refer to the strategies and principles used by educators to facilitate learning. Okoye (2020) defines them as systematic procedures that promote active engagement and improve students' academic performance. However, many educators still use lecture-based, teacher-centered approaches, which limit student participation and interaction (Ukeh et al., 2020). The traditional method, characterized by instructors dominating classroom activities while students play passive roles, often emphasizes rote memorization over critical thinking and practical application (Nwosu, 2019). Studies have shown that students frequently find conventional methods ineffective for learning computer science concepts (Eze et al., 2020; Okechukwu & Ukeh, 2022).

This situation underscores the need to explore alternative teaching strategies, such as virtual mentoring networks. Unlike the traditional approach, virtual mentoring networks provide students with real-time guidance, collaborative opportunities, and exposure to industry practices beyond the classroom. Such methods enhance practical engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, offering a more effective pathway for developing competent software engineering graduates.

Virtual mentoring networks are online platforms that connect mentors and mentees through digital communication tools to share knowledge, skills, and professional guidance. They allow learners to receive continuous support and feedback regardless of geographical distance. This system encourages collaboration, motivation, and personal growth among students, especially in technical fields like software engineering. According to Hamilton and Scandura (2019), virtual mentoring enhances accessibility to expert guidance and fosters professional development in digital learning environments. Similarly, Okoro and Oyekan (2022) noted that virtual mentoring networks bridge the gap between academic learning and real-world practice by linking students with experienced professionals online. Virtual mentoring networks are important because they connect students with experts who provide guidance, support, and collaboration that enhance learning and skill development. They also bridge the gap between classroom knowledge and real-

world practice, leading to improved students' engagement.

Students' engagement is the degree to which learners show interest, attention, and active involvement in academic activities. It reflects how emotionally and intellectually connected students are during their learning journey (Hasanov, et al. 2021). Research shows that student engagement spans emotional, behavioural and cognitive dimensions, each of which significantly predicts academic outcomes in higher education settings. (Hasanov et al., 2021; White, et al. 2022).Hopp, Stoeger, and Ziegler (2020) found that students who participated in online mentoring programs showed greater engagement and motivation, especially when peer interaction was promoted. In the same vein, Iqbal (2020) reported that e-mentoring platforms enhanced learners' participation and connection by providing consistent mentor feedback and guidance. These findings support the idea that virtual mentoring networks improve students' engagement and learning outcomes more effectively than traditional teaching approaches. Likewise, Akbari, et al. (2016) revealed that using social networking tools like Facebook boosted students' motivation, interaction, and confidence, while reducing anxiety and fostering stronger academic engagement. These findings show that virtual mentoring networks are highly effective in promoting academic success and active engagement among students, regardless of their gender.

Gender refers to the social, cultural, and psychological traits that define what it means to be male or female in a given society. It

includes the roles, behaviours, and identities that people adopt based on societal expectations and norms. According to Okafor (2020), gender goes beyond biological differences to include cultural expectations and social norms that shape individuals' identities and interactions. Gender disparity in the use of virtual mentorship networks arises when male and female students have unequal access, participation, or benefits from online mentoring opportunities, often due to differences in digital literacy and confidence levels. A study conducted by Prosper (2024), showed that male students demonstrated stronger digital literacy and higher participation in online learning platforms than female students, which led to improved engagement and better post-test performance when exposed to virtual mentoring. It is based on the above background that the present study investigated the effect of virtual mentoring networks on students' engagement in software engineering in public universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In an ideal learning environment, students in software engineering programs would actively participate in class activities, collaborate effectively with peers, and consistently demonstrate high levels of engagement, irrespective of their gender. Such engagement would foster critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and practical application of theoretical concepts, ultimately producing competent software engineers ready to meet industry demands. Ideally, virtual mentoring networks could provide personalized guidance, immediate

feedback, and professional support to students, bridging gaps between instructors and learners. This approach would ensure equal opportunities for male and female students to interact, learn, and thrive in an inclusive digital learning environment. When effectively implemented, these networks could significantly enhance students' academic performance, confidence, and readiness for real-world challenges.

However, current observations in public universities in Bayelsa State reveal low levels of student engagement in software engineering courses, with many students showing disinterest, lack of participation, and poor collaboration, particularly in gender-diverse settings. Limited access to mentoring, inadequate interaction with instructors, and insufficient peer support exacerbate this disengagement, leaving students, especially females, underrepresented in active learning spaces. The absence of structured virtual mentoring networks further widens the gap in practical skills development and professional readiness. If these challenges remain unaddressed, students risk graduating with weak competencies, low motivation, and limited employability prospects. Consequently, the failure to integrate effective virtual mentoring strategies could perpetuate gender disparities in engagement, hinder the overall quality of software engineering education, and weaken the capacity of graduates to contribute meaningfully to Nigeria's technological advancement.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of virtual mentoring networks on students' engagement in software engineering in public universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated the:

1. mean engagement scores of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method;
2. mean engagement scores of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean engagement scores of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method?
2. What are the mean engagement scores of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study and they were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean engagement scores of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean engagement scores of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks.

Research Method

Quasi-experimental pre-test post-test non-equivalent research design was adopted for this study. Quasi-experimental research design is defined as one which random assignment of subjects to experiment and control groups is not possible (Nworgu, 2015). The population consisted of 84 first year Computer Science Education students in the 2024/2025 academic session.

However, the number of students in the experimental group was 48 (40 males and 8 females) while they were 36 students in the control group. The instrument used for data collection was the *Software Engineering Engagement Test (SEET)*, which was specifically developed to assess students' engagement in software engineering activities. A score above 50 on the SEET indicated that a student demonstrated a high level of engagement in the tasks. The test measured engagement by evaluating students' attention, interest, participation, and active involvement through carefully designed questions and performance-based activities that reflected real software engineering practices. The validity of SEET was established through face and content validation, while its reliability was tested on a group of 20 Computer Science Education students in Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). The reliability coefficient of the instrument obtained using

Kuder Richardson Formula 21 was 0.82. The SEET was administered to the students both before and after the intervention. Initially, it was given as a pre-test to both the experimental and control groups to assess their engagement levels prior to implementing the virtual mentoring networks treatment.

The study involved 84 computer science education students drawn from intact software engineering classes that offers the programme. These students were divided into two groups: the experimental group, which was taught software engineering concepts using virtual mentoring networks (VMN) with structured online mentoring sessions, discussions, and feedback activities, and the control group, which received traditional face-to-face instruction without any VMN intervention. Both groups were administered the *Software Engineering Engagement Test*

(SEET) as pre-tests and post-tests to measure their level of engagement. During the study, the lecturer assigned to teach the experimental group received training on how to effectively implement VMN, including the use of online platforms, mentoring strategies, and facilitation of student discussions. Intact classes were used to maintain the natural classroom environment and reduce disruption to regular teaching schedules. The researcher influenced the teaching method by providing a structured lesson plan and guiding the lecturer on how to integrate VMN into the instructional process, ensuring consistency in the delivery of the intervention. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses. The pre-test scores served as covariates for the post-test scores at a significance level of 0.05.

Data Analysis and Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean engagement scores of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method?

Table 1: Mean engagement scores and standard deviations of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method

G r o u p s	N u m b e r	P r e - t e s t		P o s t - t e s t		M e a n D i f f e r e n c e
		M e a n ()	S t a n d a r d D e v i a t i o n ()	M e a n ()	S t a n d a r d D e v i a t i o n ()	
Experimental	4	22.55	5.09	26.39	5.89	3.84
Control	3	20.11	4.98	22.07	5.02	1.96
	84					1.88

The result presented in Table 1 shows that students taught software engineering through

virtual mentoring networks (experimental group) had higher engagement levels than

those taught with the traditional method (control group). In the pre-test, the experimental group had a mean score of **22.55** with a standard deviation of **5.09**, while the control group recorded a mean of **20.11** with a standard deviation of **4.98**. After the treatment, the experimental group’s post-test mean score rose to **26.39** (SD = 5.89), whereas the control group had **22.07** (SD =

5.02). The mean difference between the two groups was **1.88**, showing a clear improvement in engagement for the students exposed to virtual mentoring. This finding suggests that virtual mentoring networks helped students participate more actively, interact better with peers, and stay more committed to learning software engineering compared to those in traditional classrooms.

Research Question 2: What are the mean engagement scores of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks?

Table 2: Mean engagement scores and standard deviations of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks

Groups	N	Pre - test		Post - test		Mean Difference
		()	()	()	()	
Male	40	21.56	4.89	24.92	5.52	3 . 3 6
Female	8	20.44	4.35	22.31	4.90	1 . 8 7
4 8						1 . 4 9

The data in Table 2 show that male students exposed to software engineering through virtual mentoring networks had a **pre-test mean engagement score of 21.56** (SD = 4.89), while female students recorded **20.44** (SD = 4.35). After the intervention, the male students’ **post-test mean increased to 24.92** (SD = 5.52), compared to **22.31** (SD = 3.36) for the female

students. The mean difference between pre-test and post-test scores was **3.36** for males and **1.87** for females, indicating that male students experienced a greater increase in engagement. This suggests that while both genders benefited from virtual mentoring networks, male students showed higher gains in engagement than their female counterparts

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean engagement scores of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on the mean engagement scores of students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks and those using traditional method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	101.021	1	101.021	84.75	0.000
Intercept	1	1	1.000	0.84	0.361
GROUP	101.021	1			
Error	98.979	83			

The ANCOVA results in Table 3 indicate that the mean engagement scores of students differ significantly based on the method of instruction. The GROUP effect shows a Type III Sum of Squares of 101.021 with an F-value of 84.75 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant

difference. Students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks had higher engagement scores compared to those taught with the traditional method. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₁) that there is no significant difference between the two groups is rejected.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean engagement scores of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on the mean engagement scores of male and female students exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	93.021	1	93.021	158.74	0.000
Intercept	1	1	1	1.71	0.196
GENDER	93.021	1	93.021	158.74	0.000
Error	26.979	46			

The ANCOVA results in Table 4 show that the mean engagement scores of male and female students differ significantly when exposed to software engineering using virtual mentoring networks. The effect of gender has a Type III Sum of Squares of 93.021, an F-value of 158.74, and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a highly significant difference.

This suggests that either male or female students scored higher in engagement under the virtual mentoring network approach. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) that there is no significant difference between male and female students' engagement scores is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Effect of Virtual Mentoring Networks on Students' Engagement

The finding revealed that students who learned software engineering through virtual mentoring networks showed greater engagement and participation in learning activities than those taught using traditional methods. They interacted more actively with their mentors and peers, which enhanced their understanding of the subject. Their post-test mean scores were significantly higher, indicating that virtual mentoring had a strong positive impact on their academic performance and overall learning outcomes. Hopp, et al. (2020) supported this finding by showing that students involved in online mentoring programs demonstrated higher engagement and motivation, especially when peer interaction was encouraged. Similarly, Iqbal (2020) confirmed that e-mentoring platforms increased learners' engagement and active participation, as students felt more connected and motivated through consistent mentor feedback and guidance. Together, these studies align with the present finding that virtual mentoring networks enhance students' engagement and improve learning outcomes compared to traditional teaching methods. Akbari, et al. (2016) found that using online networking platforms enhanced students' motivation, interaction, and confidence in learning. In the context of software engineering, virtual mentoring networks similarly provide opportunities for peer and mentor collaboration, reducing anxiety and creating a supportive environment. This online engagement fosters both emotional and academic involvement, strengthening students' active participation

and commitment to software engineering tasks.

Gender Differences in Students' Engagement within the Experimental Group

The study showed that within the experimental group, male students demonstrated greater engagement in learning activities compared to their female counterparts. This was evident in their higher post-test scores, suggesting that they benefited more from the virtual mentoring network. The result highlights a clear gender difference in performance, indicating that male students may adapt more quickly or participate more actively in technology-based mentoring environments. Lin, et al. (2021) agree with this finding because gender differences influenced the quality and outcomes of mentoring relationships, with male students often benefiting more from mentor interactions due to greater confidence and engagement in virtual mentoring environments. The finding also agree with **Prosper (2024)** who posited that male students demonstrated stronger digital literacy and higher participation levels in online learning platforms than female students, which contributed to their improved engagement and better post-test performance when exposed to virtual mentoring.

Conclusion

The study concluded that virtual mentoring networks are effective in enhancing students' engagement in software engineering. Students exposed to this approach demonstrated stronger understanding and better performance than those taught through

traditional methods. This suggests that technology-driven mentoring can significantly improve learning engagement. The use of virtual mentoring also encourages collaboration and continuous feedback, which support deeper learning. Therefore, integrating virtual mentoring networks into university teaching is a valuable strategy for improving the effective teaching and learning of software engineering.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Public universities should integrate virtual mentoring networks into software engineering courses to enhance student engagement, motivation, and active participation.
2. Lecturers should receive training on effectively using virtual mentoring tools and facilitating online interactions to maximize student learning outcomes.
3. Universities should encourage the use of technology-driven instructional methods alongside traditional teaching to create a supportive and interactive learning environment for students.

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